

From Power Spectral Density to Infinite Phase Screens Generation: towards hybrid simulation strategies in Adaptive Optics

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ABSTRACT

We present a hybrid simulation strategy for Adaptive Optics (AO) systems that bridges Power Spectral Density (PSD)-based and covariance-based methods for generating infinite phase screens representing residual (uncorrected) wavefront phases. Starting from a closed-loop AO simulation in SPECULA, we extract the spatial PSD of the residual phase, derive the 1D PSD profile, and apply a Hankel transform to compute the spatial covariance. This information is then used to generate an Infinite Phase Screen, whose time-varying component is completed by adding a modal noise to it, which represents the propagation of the WFS noise and spatial aliasing within the closed-loop system. We demonstrate this approach in the context of the ANDES SCAO system for the ELT, showing that the residual simulation reproduces the Strehl ratio of the full simulation with high fidelity. This method is particularly suited for cascading AO systems, petal mode control, and any application that requires a compact, yet statistically accurate, representation of AO residuals.

Keywords: Adaptive Optics, Infinite Phase Screen, Power Spectral Density, Simulation, ELT, ANDES, Residual Phase.

1. INTRODUCTION

The simulation of adaptive optics (AO) systems requires efficient and accurate representations of atmospheric turbulence and its residual after correction. The main methods for atmospheric turbulence simulation can be broadly divided into two categories. PSD/FFT-based methods[5] are easy to implement and computationally fast, but are limited to finite phase screens, use static statistics, and have large memory requirements. Covariance-based methods[1] can generate infinite phase screens with dynamic statistics and small memory requirements, but their implementation is more complex and computationally slower.

The core idea of this work is to use an Infinite Phase Screen of defined statistics to represent the evolution of the residual (uncorrected) phase from an AO system. This approach aims to facilitate the simulation and evaluation of the concatenation of AO systems. Possible use cases include:

- Extension of AO systems by adding a second deformable mirror or wavefront sensor (as in SPHERE[3]);
- Cascading different AO loops for petal modes and atmospheric turbulence (as in ANDES[4][6], GMT, and MORFEO);
- Evaluation of AO performance on test benches such as STILES[2].

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$$\Phi(k) = 2\pi \int_0^\infty C(r) J_0(kr) r dr \quad C(r) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \Phi(k) J_0(kr) k dk$$

Figure 1. Spatial covariance and PSD as a Hankel transform/anti-transform pair.

We elaborate on the method from Assémat et al.[1], implementing it in our simulation framework SPECULA[7] to run on the GPU for improved speed, and extending it to handle any wind direction.

2. OUR APPROACH

2.1 Overview of the Method

As demonstrated by Tatarski[8], the spatial PSD and the spatial covariance function form a Hankel transform/anti-transform pair of order 0, shown in Fig.1. This relationship can be exploited in both symbolic and numerical computations.

The proposed approach consists of five main steps:

1. **Full ANDES SCAO simulation in SPECULA:** Run a closed-loop simulation to collect the residual phase time series at the Deformable Mirror (DM) output. See Fig.2 (a).
2. **2D PSD from Phase Cube:** Compute the spatial Power Spectral Density (2D) of the residual phase cube. See Fig.2 (b).
3. **1D PSD Profile Extraction:** Reconstruct the 1D PSD radial profile. See Fig.3 (a). Please note that a direct azimuthal integration of the 2D PSD is often insufficient due to boundary conditions, numerical artifacts, and spatial sampling constraints. Therefore, we implemented a dedicated extraction pipeline detailed in the following sequential operations:
 - (a) **1D profile extraction:** Extract the 1D profile resulting from the azimuthal integration of the 2D PSD.
 - (b) **Frequency clipping:** Clip the low and high spatial frequencies. This operation is applied to soften the “diffraction” effects (spectral leakage) introduced by the sharp boundaries of the telescope pupil.
 - (c) **Profile smoothing:** Perform a smoothing of the profile. This step further dampens any residual diffraction-like ringing originating from the pupil mask, and it effectively eliminates high-frequency numerical noise and artificial artifacts introduced by the discrete Fourier transform and the finite grid sampling.
 - (d) **High-frequency extension:** Extend the clipped PSD for high frequencies based on *a priori* knowledge of the actual residual spectrum. The simulated PSD profile is inherently limited by the finite dimensions of the 2D arrays used in the numerical simulations. Beyond the spatial sampling limit of the deformable mirror actuators, the residual phase will naturally follow the theoretical slope of the atmospheric turbulence spectrum.

Figure 2. (a) One sample of the residual Phase out of the End-to-end simulation in step 1, (b) The 2D PSD resulting from step 2 (c) A sample of the final residual phase generated by our method, in step 5.

Figure 3. (a) The extraction of a 1D PSD profile in step 3, (b) The covariance function resulting from step 4.

4. **Hankel Transform:** Apply a Hankel transform (order 0) to compute the spatial covariance from the 1D PSD. See Fig.3 (b) for an example of the result.
5. **Residual Phase Generation:** Perform an alternative simulation using an Infinite Phase Screen driven by the computed spatial covariance, combined with a time-varying modal noise component that models the spatiotemporal error (WFS noise and spatial aliasing) propagation within the closed-loop system. See Fig.2 (c). Details about the temporal component of the residual are given in Sect.2.2.

2.2 Residual Phase Model

The residual phase model is composed of two main components:

1. **Infinite Phase Screen:** This component, initialized from the 2D spatial PSD of the AO residuals, represents the spatially correlated, low-frequency component of the residual phase. It is extended over time by adding columns and/or rows (depending on the wind direction), reproducing the wind speed on the residual phase screen. The PSD used to seed the initial screen is an extended version of the Von Karman PSD, filtered to include only the spatial frequencies above the AO correction bandwidth ($f > f_{AO}$), with an additional piston filter applied.
2. **Modal Noise (Temporal):** A time-varying component representing the spatio-temporal propagation of errors within the closed-loop system. It specifically accounts for Wavefront Sensor (WFS) measurement noise and spatial aliasing, capturing the dynamic, low-spatial-frequency residual errors characteristic of AO correction.

The method requires as input the spatial PSD to generate the initial phase screen and the spatial covariance to extend it over time.

Figure 4. Comparison of the temporal PSDs for the full simulation and a simulation using the Infinite Phase Screen and modal noise model, (a) Mode 0, (b) Mode 9, (c) Mode 99.

2.3 Proof-of-Concept Case: ANDES SCAO

For this proof of concept, we consider the case of the ANDES Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO) system for the ELT. We assume the wind-driven evolution of the residual is dominated by a single layer moving at a fixed wind speed.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

We implemented the simulation to produce the initial 2D PSD (steps 1 and 2) and the final residual simulation (step 5) directly within SPECULA. The Infinite Phase Screen is a SPECULA processing object that can be used for both ordinary atmospheric layer simulation and for residual phase modeling. Steps 3 and 4 (1D PSD profile extraction and Hankel transform) are implemented as additional Python scripts that interface with the SPECULA framework.

The implementation runs on the GPU to achieve competitive computational speeds compared to full closed-loop simulations. The Infinite Phase Screen object in SPECULA is designed to be generic and reusable, supporting any wind direction through appropriate extension of the phase screen along arbitrary axes.

4. RESULTS

We compared the Strehl ratio obtained from two simulations: (1) the full ANDES SCAO closed-loop simulation in SPECULA, and (2) the residual simulation using the Infinite Phase Screen and modal noise model derived from the full simulation.

The results show excellent agreement between the two approaches (see Figs. 4 and 5):

- Full Simulation Strehl: 0.8950 ± 0.0044
- Residual Model Simulation Strehl: 0.8979 ± 0.0063

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Comparison between full simulation and a simulation using the Infinite Phase Screen and modal noise model. (a), modal standard deviation computed projecting the residual wavefront on a modal base with 4000 modes, (b), time history of the K band Strehl Ratio.

The close match in both the mean Strehl ratio and its temporal variability demonstrates that the Infinite Phase Screen model, driven by the PSD of the AO residuals and augmented by a time-varying modal noise term, can faithfully reproduce the statistical properties of the residual wavefront as seen in a full closed-loop simulation. Although minor discrepancies are visible in the temporal PSDs (Fig. 4) and modal standard deviations (Figs. 5), they are well within acceptable margins and do not hinder the ultimate goal of our approach. This effectively validates our hybrid simulation strategy as a robust, computationally efficient tool for representing and propagating AO residuals.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed and implemented a hybrid simulation strategy that combines PSD/FFT-based and covariance-based methods to generate Infinite Phase Screens representing the residual phase of an AO system. The approach was validated on the ANDES SCAO use case, showing that a compact residual model can reproduce the Strehl performance of a full closed-loop simulation with high fidelity.

The early-stage results are promising. We plan to refine the method by modeling more accurately the time-varying component (modal noise) and to verify its accuracy in the case of a multi-layer atmosphere model. We foresee several possible applications, as stated in the introduction, and we look forward to testing it more extensively in simulation and on data acquired on an AO test bench. In particular, the STILES test bench available in Arcetri, described in Azzaroli et al.[2], offers a concrete opportunity to validate the approach on real AO system data.

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